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Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Prestressed Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge

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Abstract:	<p>This paper describes the first application of Electrically Isolated Tendon (EIT) technology in the United States. These systems have been developed to provide a level of quality assurance for post-tensioned strand systems in bridge applications. The EIT system is intended to provide electrical isolation between the strand inside the post-tensioning duct and the reinforcement outside of the duct system thus reducing the potential for corrosion to occur. This is achieved using plastic tendon ducts, additional protection of the ducts, modified tendon trumpets, electrical isolation plates at the tendon anchorages, and encapsulation of the strand anchors. A demonstration was conducted with support of the FHWA and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. The system consists of a three-span continuous bridge composed of pretensioned Pennsylvania Bulb tees spliced and post-tensioned. The bridge system was monitored during beam fabrication, erection and bridge construction and an overview of the EIT installation methodology is presented. The performance of the EIT system is compared with standard recommendations on acceptable performance and was found to meet the requirements. Installation of the EIT system was not significantly different than that of a conventional post-tensioning tendon. The system provided additional assurance of the electrical isolation in the bridge and appears to be a viable approach for long term monitoring of the performance of post-tensioned grouted tendons.</p>	
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<p>If your answer is yes, please explain in the comments box below.</p> <p>as follow-up to "Is this article or parts of it already published in print or online in any language? ASCE does not review content already published (see next questions for conference papers and posted theses/dissertations). If your answer is yes, please explain in the comments box below."</p>	A short two page synopsis on the bridge was written for and published in PCI Aspire magazine in Spring 2019. It is freely available through PCI website. Some repetition from the Aspire article may be present but the submitted article to ASCE is much more comprehensive and contains alot more detail as well as the results of the measurements.
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Submitted to ASCE Bridge Journal

1 **CONSTRUCTION AND FIELD EVALUATION OF ELECTRICALLY ISOLATED**
2 **TENDONS IN A PRESTRESSED CONCRETE SPLICED GIRDER BRIDGE**

3 **Clay Naito, Ph.D., P.E.¹**

4 **ABSTRACT**

5 This paper describes the first application of Electrically Isolated Tendon (EIT) technology in the United States. These
6 systems have been developed to provide a level of quality assurance for post-tensioned strand systems in bridge
7 applications. The EIT system is intended to provide electrical isolation between the strand inside the post-tensioning
8 duct and the reinforcement outside of the duct system thus reducing the potential for corrosion to occur. This is
9 achieved using plastic tendon ducts, additional protection of the ducts, modified tendon trumpets, electrical isolation
10 plates at the tendon anchorages, and encapsulation of the strand anchors. A demonstration was conducted with support
11 of the FHWA and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. The system consists of a three-span continuous bridge
12 composed of pretensioned Pennsylvania Bulb tees spliced and post-tensioned. The bridge system was monitored
13 during beam fabrication, erection and bridge construction and an overview of the EIT installation methodology is
14 presented. The performance of the EIT system is compared with standard recommendations on acceptable
15 performance and was found to meet the requirements. Installation of the EIT system was not significantly different
16 than that of a conventional post-tensioning tendon. The system provided additional assurance of the electrical isolation
17 in the bridge and appears to be a viable approach for long term monitoring of the performance of post-tensioned
18 grouted tendons.

19 **CE Database subject headings:** Prestressed; Monitoring; Spliced Girders; Construction

20

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21 **Post-Tensioned Bridge System Performance Concerns**

22 Post-tensioning (PT) systems have been successfully used for moderate span bridge construction since the 1950s and
23 continues to be an effective method of construction for major U.S. construction projects such as the San Francisco
24 Oakland Bay Bridge East Span completed in 2013. One of the principal issues regarding the use of grouted post-
25 tensioned duct systems is the inability to readily inspect the grout placement within the ducts and the condition of the
26 tendons during construction and service. Issues that can arise include: (1) voids due to insufficient grouting which can
27 result in water accumulation from initial bleed or through intrusion; (2) physical grout deficiencies such as the inability
28 to set, segregate, or the formation of soft regions; (3) elevated chloride content of the grout due to errors in
29 manufacturing of the prepackaged mix (Hartt and Lee 2018); (4) infiltration of chloride laden water during service
30 due to poor detailing; (5) unexpected cracking in plastic ducts (Suarez et al. 2006). All of these issues can result in
31 corrosion initiation in the tendons and if left unchecked can result in significant damage and the potential for closure
32 of the bridge. Such damage has been observed sporadically for post-tensioned bridge systems over the past 50 years,
33 as noted in Table 1. The degree of damage observed varied and included significant tendon corrosion, complete failure
34 of tendons, and in some extreme cases, complete collapse of the bridge. Note that no known collapses of post-tensioned
35 systems have occurred in the U.S. due to the biennial safety inspections conducted as part of federally mandated
36 standards of care. In addition, issues such as the elevated grout chlorides have been addressed and mitigated in U.S.
37 construction. Nevertheless, in many cases, even those where the tendons did not reach the point of failure, the
38 corrosion observed was significant enough to result in bridge closure and significant repairs to the system.

39 While strict quality control methods can be implemented to improve performance of materials and non-destructive
40 evaluation methods can be employed during construction, unexpected problems with the PT system such as accidental
41 leakage at joints or poor drainage cannot be easily detected. Electrically isolated tendon (EIT) systems can be
42 implemented to address these concerns. This paper provides an overview of an EIT system and a case study of its
43 implementation and performance in a Pennsylvania bridge.

44 **EIT Tendon Systems**

45 EIT has been developed for internal grouted post-tensioning applications to provide an increased level of corrosion
46 protection and to provide monitoring capability of the tendons during construction and service. A sufficient level of
47 isolation for a typical bridge service life can be achieved with the use of corrugated plastic ducts (polyethylene or

48 polypropylene) combined with traditional post-tension anchorage and splice hardware. A highest level of corrosion
49 protection can be achieved with a complete EIT system which can provide full electrical isolation of the PT tendons
50 within the duct from reinforcement in the beam. This requires the use of electrically isolated anchor heads, plastic
51 ducts, and special care at grout vents and splices. Detailing of EITs is critical to the effective implementation of the
52 system, particularly near the anchorages in order to ensure complete encapsulation and electrical isolation. While
53 initial implementation of plastic ducts occurred in the 1960's a concerted effort to develop a full EIT system did not
54 take place until the 1985 construction of the Zurich railway station which required special protection against the stray
55 currents at the station (Elsener 2004). The EIT concept has been examined in depth by Elsener and others (Elsener
56 2004; Vedova and Elsener 2006). EIT systems have been used in various post-tensioned concrete bridges in Europe,
57 including the Piacenza Viaduct and Marchiazza Viaduct in Italy and the P.S. du Milieu and the Wiesebrücke Basel in
58 Switzerland. Guidelines are available on the use of the system from the Swiss (Elsener and Buechler 2011), the
59 International Federation for Structural Concrete fib 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005), and a draft guideline is under
60 development for U.S. applications (Angst and Buchler 2015). The Post-Tensioning Institute and the American
61 Segmental Bridge Institute also outlines approaches that can be followed to achieve various levels of protection (Post-
62 Tensioning Institute (PTI) and American Segmental Bridge Institute (ASBI) 2012).

63 The goal of the EIT system is to provide complete encapsulation of the tendon from the material exterior to the tendon.
64 The system can be represented as a circuit as illustrated in Figure 1. The AC impedance is measured between the
65 encapsulated tendon and the reinforcement within the concrete member. As part of the circuit, the grout acts as a
66 resistor, the tendon/duct/reinforcement a capacitor, and the concrete a resistor. The presence of any defects along the
67 length of the duct will act in parallel to the capacitor resulting in a significant decrease in the impedance between the
68 tendon and the reinforcing steel.

69 ***Recommended EIT Measurements***

70 The AC impedance measurements for the EIT system consists of the resistance, capacitance and loss factor (Angst
71 and Buchler 2015). The resistance, R , is the measurement of the resistance between the encapsulated tendon and the
72 steel reinforcement in the surrounding concrete. High values of resistance are indicative of a high level of
73 encapsulation. Large breaches in the system combined with moisture will result in very low resistance between the
74 tendon within the duct and the reinforcement outside the duct. Consequently, the magnitude of the resistance and
75 changes in the resistance over time can be used as an indicator of the effectiveness and temporal changes in the

76 encapsulation. The post-tensioning system also acts as a capacitor, with the tendon acting as one conductive material,
77 the conventional reinforcement acting as the other, and the polyethylene duct acting as a dielectric between the two
78 conductors. A change in the capacitance is indicative of a change in the permittivity (i.e., a change in the dielectric
79 properties) due to changes in the integrity of the duct. A real capacitor will have some resistive current running between
80 conductive materials and can be modeled as an equivalent series resistor (ESR) in series with an ideal capacitor. The
81 loss factor, also commonly referred to as the dissipation factor, provides a measure of the dielectric material's ability
82 to absorb energy when an AC signal is applied. The loss factor is the ratio of the real and imaginary components of
83 the impedance (Angst and Buchler 2015). Increases in the loss factor are indicative of higher energy dissipation in the
84 real capacitor which is indicative of problems with the encapsulation.

85 Measurements are typically taken at one end of the bridge but provide an assessment of the integrity of the entire
86 tendon length, L . Since the tendon and reinforcement have negligible resistance, the presence of defects in the tendon
87 encapsulation at any point along the duct length will result in a decrease in resistance or increase in capacitance and
88 loss factor. The resistance and capacitance are normalized by the tendon length resulting in the specific resistance, R_i ,
89 and specific capacitance, C_i , for the system as noted in Equation 1 and 2.

90
$$R_i = R \cdot L \quad [\Omega \cdot m] \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

91
$$C_i = C/L \quad [F/m] \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

92 The loss factor, D , is a unitless term which is independent of the length of the duct and increases in magnitude with
93 the number of defects.

94 The standard measurements taken for an EIT system include the resistance, capacitance, and loss factor. It is important
95 to note that the measurements are sensitive to the excitation voltage, measuring frequency and the temperature of the
96 system. The details of the bridge including the length of the EIT tendon, the date and time of the reading, and the
97 temperature should be noted. The impedance measurements can be taken with a portable
98 Inductance/Capacitance/Resistance (LCR) meter as noted schematically in Figure 1 and shown in Figure 2. As noted
99 in fib bulletin 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005, 33), the measurements should be taken with the LCR meter set in
100 parallel to the EIT circuit with a measuring frequency of 1 kHz and a minimum AC excitation voltage of 0.5 V.

101 **Coplay Bridge Demonstration**

102 A demonstration project was implemented by the Federal Highway Administration and Pennsylvania Department of
103 Transportation in collaboration with Northampton and Lehigh County to assess the viability, ease of use, and operation

104 of the EIT system. The bridge system consists of precast/prestressed Pennsylvania bulb tee girders spliced and post-
105 tensioned in place. The bridge is part of a replacement project conducted by Pennsylvania Department of
106 Transportation (PennDOT) on behalf of Lehigh County. The bridge crosses from Lehigh to Northampton County on
107 State Route 7404. The bridge is located in the borough of Coplay and is herein referred to as the Coplay Bridge
108 (pronounced kăp lâ). The bridge consists of eight spans bridging over Bridge Street, the Ironton Rail Trail, the Lehigh
109 River, and the Norfolk Southern Rail Road Line. The bridge consists of three approach spans to the west of the river
110 (Spans 1, 2 and 3) and two approach spans to the east of the river (Spans 7 and 8). A spliced post-tensioned girder
111 system is utilized for the main spans of the bridge (Span 4, 5 and 6). Five spliced prestressed / post-tensioned concrete
112 PA bulb tees spaced at approximately 3.12m (10'-3") are used across the 13.62 m (44' - 8 1/4") wide deck.

113 ***EIT System***

114 The project was competitively bid and the contractor selected Dywidag Systems International (DSI) to provide the
115 post-tensioning system. Each of the five beam lines contained four post-tensioning ducts with each duct containing
116 fifteen 0.6 in. (15 mm) diameter grade 270 low relaxation strands conforming to ASTM A416 (ASTM International
117 2017, 416). To compare conventional and EIT construction details both systems were integrated into each beam. The
118 top tendon line in each beam was designed with full isolation, the bottom three were designed with standard hardware.
119 The fabrication was conducted in two phases: plant fabrication and field operations. The pretensioned beams were
120 precast at Northeast Prestressed Products in Cressona, PA. The field operations included the delivery, via truck 72.4
121 km (45 miles), erection onsite by Structural Services, beam splicing, placement of closure joints, post-tension
122 application, and the diaphragms and deck placement by Trumbull Corporation. Details of these two phases with
123 respect to the EIT system are outlined in the following sections.

124 ***Plant Fabrication***

125 Both tendon systems include an anchorage head, trumpet, duct, and couplers. The duct system in both cases are
126 comprised of 85 mm (3.35 in.) internal diameter corrugated polypropylene ducts with O.D. of 100.2 mm (3.95 in.)
127 and wall thickness of 2.54 mm (0.10 in.) conforming to ASTM D4101 (ASTM Standard D4101-17 2017). To provide
128 isolation of the tendon all strands are encapsulated through special detailing from one anchor head to the other. The
129 anchor head is covered with a plastic grout cap and the grout tube is sealed with a polyethylene cap after the grout has
130 hardened. The strand wedges and wedge plate are steel but they bear on a non-conductive electrical isolation plate
131 attached to the metal anchor body. A plastic trumpet is used within the anchor body and includes a lip which is

132 sandwiched between the isolation plate and anchor body thus preventing electrical continuity of the tendon grout
133 (Figure 4). Ducts are coupled with a polypropylene slip-on coupler and sealed with heat shrink sleeves field cut to 111
134 mm (4 3/8 in.). Grout vents and drains are fabricated by drilling holes in the duct and creating a weld with the
135 polyethylene port connection. To minimize potential damage to the ducts during fabrication and stressing protective
136 half-shells are used where the duct is supported by transverse reinforcement and secured using plastic zip ties (Figure
137 5). Following precast operations the ducts were inspected to ensure that no obstructions were present in the duct. A
138 steel cylinder, sized to match the area of strands expected, was run through each duct and no conflicts were found.
139 The ducts were then capped at each end to prevent any debris or moisture from entering the ducts during storage and
140 transportation. The precast producer found no tangible difference in the installation labor between the EIT and non-
141 EIT anchorage heads, trumpets, ducts and couplers.

142 ***Field Construction***

143 The beams were erected on the completed piers and two temporary shoring towers as noted in Figure 3 and shown in
144 Figure 6. Strongbacks were used to provide temporary bracing and to assist with alignment at each closure joint (Figure
145 6). The ducts were spliced at each closure joint in the field using a polypropylene coupler sealed with heat shrink
146 sleeves field cut to 111 mm (4 3/8 in.). The required splice distance between beams at the closure joint location was
147 designated as 305 mm (12 in.). This limited space required any coupling materials to be placed over the extended
148 ducts prior to erection. To properly measure the level of electrical isolation in the tendon along the bridge length, the
149 electrical continuity of the conventional reinforcement in each spliced beam needed to be maintained. As illustrated
150 in Figure 5, pretensioning strands were used in each beam segment to ensure continuity. These bare strands were tied
151 to the transverse reinforcement cage within each beam during plant fabrication, thus providing steel-to-steel contact
152 within the body of each beam. At the end of each precast beam segment two of the pretensioning strands were left
153 extending 25.4 cm (10 in.) from each face. These strands were overlapped 203 mm (8 in.) and fastened together at
154 each closure joint ensure electrical continuity of all the reinforcement along the length of the bridge. Note that two
155 strands were used to provide redundancy. Details of the field connections are illustrated in Figure 6.

156 Once the closure pours were completed, the strands were run through the ducts, the isolation plates and wedge plates
157 were installed, and stressing was conducted. The tendons were stressed from both ends one at a time once the concrete
158 in all the closure pours had reached the minimum required strength. After stressing, the duct was pressurized to 138
159 kPa (20 psi) internal pressure with oil and water-free compressed air. The pressure integrity was checked by locking

160 off the outside air source for 1 minute. The test was required in the design specification and was intended to check for
161 leaks in the duct system prior to grout placement and was not intended to be an air-tightness test of the system. During
162 the pre-grouting air pressure test, beam D exhibited a marginal loss of pressure. The leak was identified as cross-
163 communication between the adjacent ducts. While the exact location could not be identified it is likely that a pathway
164 may have formed through the heat shrink splice at one of the closure joints. The remaining ducts were able to hold
165 pressure without incident.

166 The ducts were grouted within 7 days of stressing. The grout was required to meet a number of performance
167 requirements including: chloride permeability of less than 2500 coulombs tested in accordance with ASTM C1202
168 (ASTM Standard C1202-19 2019), chloride ion content less than 0.08% by weight of cementitious material, set time
169 between 3 and 12 hours tested in accordance with ASTM C953 (ASTM Standard C953-17 2017), and grout strength
170 greater than 20.7 MPa (3 ksi) at 7 days and 34.5 MPa (5 ksi) at 28 days tested in accordance with ASTM C942 (ASTM
171 Standard C942-15 2015). A special inspection of all anchorage outlets and high point outlets was performed after 24
172 hours to identify the presence of soft grout. The grout mix consisted of 22.7 kg (50 lbs) of Euclid PTX with 5.7 to 6.4
173 liters (1.5 to 1.7 gal) of potable water. Pretesting of the grout met all requirements. The grout was tested with both
174 water levels and resulted in a set time of 9.5 to 11 hours, 0.011% chloride by weight of mixed grout, rapid chloride
175 permeability ranging from 306 to 388 coulombs at 28 days, compressive strength of 49 to 58 MPa (7110 to 8470 psi)
176 at 7 days and 68 to 75 MPa (9880 to 10900 psi) at 28 days. Soft grout was not observed on the bridge.

177 To facilitate intermittent monitoring of the EIT system a junction box was installed on the pier of the bridge. The
178 measurements were taken at pier 3. As previously mentioned, the top tendon in each beam was fully encapsulated and
179 the remaining three were conventionally constructed. One lead wire (AWG #12 Copper wire double sheathed) was
180 attached to the wedge plate with a hex head screw. This connection was encapsulated in grout within the plastic
181 anchorage grout cap as illustrated in Figure 6. These connections are denoted AE through EE, for beams A through E
182 in Figure 2. Two additional connections were made to each strand in each beam, denoted AS1 and AS2 for beam A
183 to ES1 and ES2 for beam E. These three wires were run to a junction box near the ground on Pier 3, Figure 2. For
184 simplicity all reinforcement measurements were connected together. Readings were taken from the box and directly
185 from the beam end at time of installation to ensure that the additional cable run did not result in any change in readings.

186 **Monitoring and Performance**

187 Field impedance measurements of the EIT tendons were conducted at key stages in construction. The first
188 measurement was prior to tensioning and after tensioning but prior to grouting. The purpose of these measurements
189 are to first ensure that a short is not present between the tendon and the beam reinforcement. Assuming that a high
190 AC resistance is measured, the post-tensioning measurement ensures that the ducts were not damaged during
191 tensioning operations. The next measurement taken was immediately following grouting. At this point the resistance
192 drops precipitously due to the encasement of the PT tendons in the wet grout. Measurements were taken regularly
193 with the key measurements taken at 28 days after grout placement. Additional measurements were taken during
194 placement of the beam diaphragms and deck. All measurements were taken with a BK Precision model 880 LCR
195 meter with excitation voltage set at 0.6 V and test frequency of 1 kHz. The specific resistance measurements are
196 summarized in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 7. The specific capacitance and loss factor measurements are
197 illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 9. It is important to note that the standard, non-EIT, tendons are not isolated from
198 the beam reinforcement. Impedance checks of the standard PT tendons after grouting indicated electrical continuity
199 as expected and no further monitoring was conducted.

200 **Acceptance Criteria**

201 Acceptable performance of the system is assessed at various stages. After stressing the AC resistance of the strands
202 should be greater than 10 Ohms (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005). Values less than this are indicative of direct contact
203 between the tendon strands and beam steel. At this stage the capacitance and loss factor are not measured since grout
204 is not present. At an age of 28 days after grouting the Coplay bridge required a specific resistance greater than 50
205 kOhm-m. This value is in accordance with U.S. draft guidelines (Angst and Buchler 2015) which also permit up to a
206 10% failure rate for bridges where basic monitoring is conducted. For special situations where fatigue loading controls
207 or stray current is present, higher requirements are prescribed. The fib bulletin 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005)
208 prescribes acceptable performance based on the duct diameter. Laboratory testing was conducted on a specific duct
209 known as PT-Plus which is different than what was used in the Coplay Bridge. For 76 mm PT-Plus ducts the specific
210 resistance should be greater than 400kOhm-m, less than 3.05 nF/m, and have a loss factor less than 0.1. The specific
211 resistance and capacitance change to 300 kOhm-m and 3.35 nF/m for 100 mm ducts. These values have been removed
212 from recent recommendations including the U.S. draft standard since thresholds vary based on duct material and wall

213 thickness. Additional research is needed to develop these values for each commercially available system before limits
214 can be prescribed.

215 The EIT tendons in each of the five beams performed in accordance with the design specification requirements. High
216 resistance values were observed both prior and following post-tensioning operations. This indicated that the beams
217 did not have any major shorts prior to grouting. The tendons all achieved the 50 kOhm-m specific resistance
218 requirement 7-days after grouting. By the required age of 28 days the specific resistances ranged from 137 to 254
219 kOhm-m. While the fib bulletin 33 requirements were not required for the bridge a comparison shows that: (1) the
220 tendons exceeded the specific resistance of 300 kOhm-m at an age of 86 days, (2) the specific capacitance was less
221 than the control value of 3.05 nF/m at all ages, and (3) the loss factor approached a value of 0.10 as the concrete and
222 grout cured but only dropped below that value in beam A and B at an age of 86 days, and in all beams at an age of
223 352 days. Recall that the validity of the fib 33 requirements were not established for the duct used in the Copley
224 project. Beam line D which had marginal pressure loss due to cross-communication between the ducts resulted with
225 the lowest initial specific resistance and highest specific capacitance readings as noted in Table 2. The resistance
226 improved rapidly as the grout cured leaving beam line C with the lowest resistance. As illustrated in Figures 7, 8 and
227 9, the specific resistance measurements appear to provide the most sensitivity to variations in encapsulation.

228 In general, the readings followed expected trends during the Fall construction season. The specific resistance
229 increased, the capacitance and loss factors decreased. Construction was put on hold for the Winter and once the
230 temperature reached reasonable levels, concrete placement restarted. The first Spring measurement was taken at a
231 grout age of 167 days. This reading was taken within a week of placement of the east end diaphragm at Pier 6. At this
232 stage a measurable decrease in resistance and increases in capacitance and loss factor were noted. It is expected that
233 the presence of freshly placed concrete surrounding the east end of the tendon run resulted in the measured changes.
234 Further measurements of the system taken at 185 days, a week after completion of the west end diaphragm at Pier 3,
235 showed a reversal of the unexpected trend. The remaining construction consists of deck placement which due to the
236 presence of epoxy coated bars was not expected to change the trend of the readings. Measurements at an age of 352
237 days indicates that the specific resistance values continued to increase as expected. Ambient temperature
238 measurements were taken during each reading and are noted in Table 2. While a focused thermal study was not
239 conducted, it does not appear that variations in temperature resulted in significant changes in measured impedance.

240 **Recommendations**

241 Based on discussion with contractors and precast fabricators the EIT system did not require measurable increases in
242 fabrication effort. Additional recommendations were suggested to improve quality assurance along the way. To help
243 ensure the performance of the precast units a preliminary pressure check of the beams at the plant would be beneficial
244 to ensure that they are sound before transportation and erection. This check could include a low pressure check prior
245 to concrete placement at the plant and following initial curing. The closure joint spacing of 305 mm (12 in.) made
246 splicing of the plastic ducts very difficult in the field. An increase in this distance would ease installation of couplers
247 and proper attachment of heat shrink tubing, as an alternative, an improved coupling system would be advantageous.

248 To further understand the implications of the measurements taken additional research is needed. This should include
249 characterization of acceptable specific capacitance and loss factors for the variety of ducts commercially available.
250 These tests should also examine the impact of coupling techniques on the measured performance. Sensitivity tests
251 should be completed to illustrate the impact of defect size and chloride intrusion on measurable changes in the specific
252 resistance. The impact of grout type and inherent chloride content should also be examined.

253 **Conclusions**

254 An electrically isolated tendon (EIT) system was demonstrated in the Copley Bridge replacement project. The bridge
255 system is composed of precast pretensioned Pennsylvania bulb tee beams that are field spliced and post-tensioned.
256 This is the first application of EIT technology in the United States. An overview of the system was discussed along
257 with detailing and measurement requirements.

258 The EIT system appears to provide a viable system for initial and long term monitoring of encapsulation of the PT
259 tendon. Installation of the EIT system was not significantly different than that of a conventional post-tensioning tendon
260 and did not require any noticeable labor increase during precast or field operations. The system provided additional
261 assurance of the electrical isolation in the bridge and appears to be a viable approach for long term monitoring of the
262 performance of the tendons. Additional research is recommended to allow for better understanding of the performance
263 of the system during long term monitoring and for establishment of a more comprehensive acceptance criteria.

264 **Data Availability Statement**

265 All data, models, and code generated or used during the study appear in the submitted article.

266 **Acknowledgements**

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331 **List of Tables**

332 Table 1: Sample cases of post-tension tendon corrosion

333 Table 2: Specific resistance measurements for Coplay Bridge

334

Bridge Name	Bridge Type	Location	Year	Observed Damage	Causes of Corrosion
Bickton Meadows Footbridge	Precast Segmental	UK	1967	Bridge Collapse	Mortar joints allowed moisture, chlorides and oxygen transport at joints (Trejo et al. 2009)
Ynys-Y-Gwas (Woodward 1981)	Segmental PT	Wales	1985	Bridge Collapse	Transverse joints between segments filled with dry mortar caulking allowing water infiltration (Trejo et al. 2009)
Malle Bridge (Mathy et al. 1996)	Precast Segmental	Belgium	1992	Bridge Collapse	Voids in duct and ingress of water and chlorides
Niles Channel Bridge (Powers, Sagüés, and Virmani, n.d.)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	1999	Tendon Failure	Water infiltration into tendon anchorage with voids
Mid Bay Bridge (Corven Engineering, Inc. 2001)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	2000	Tendon Failure	Cracked post tensioning ducts and exposed strand along water bleed trails
Sunshine Skyway	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder / Cable Stay	Florida	2000	Tendon Failure	Poor grout quality/practices, voids near anchorage, cracked polyethylene ducts, water infiltration through segmental joints (Trejo et al. 2009)
Varina-Enon Bridge	Cable Stay with PT Box Girder	Virginia	2001	Tendon Failure	Voids in tendons and absence of grout (Trejo et al. 2009)
Plymouth Ave Bridge (Berg and Schokker 2012)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Minnesota	2010	Tendon Failure	Leak in drainage system internal to box and corrosion of lower box tendon
Ringling Causeway (Goldsberry 2013)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	2011	Tendon Failure	Deficient Grout (Grout having high moisture content, high pore water pH, low total chloride concentrations and high sulfate concentrations)

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336

Tendon Lengths [m]:		166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92
Beam ID		AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Age of Grout [days]	Temperature [C]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]
Prior to Tension	4.4	26693	13280	9877	19754	11474
Post-Tension	N.A.	28695	11786	7325	27409	18588
0	N.A.	35	41	20	10	23
1	10.0	53	61	33	42	32
3	1.7	81	92	49	77	58
7	5.0	92	104	55	96	65
9	15.6	98	112	56	108	72
14	10.0	141	154	83	149	N.A.
16	7.2	171	172	90	178	119
17	3.3	211	196	106	212	144
28	5.6	254	246	137	223	168
42	3.3	296	298	156	257	203
86	-5.6	656	581	370	451	484
167	15.6	450	388	219	279	264
185	13.3	535	457	253	340	327
352	22.2	1081	947	600	628	657

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338

339 **Data Appendix**

340 The following tables provide the data for the values included in Figures 8 and 9. These can be included as an appendix
341 to the paper at the discretion of the editor.

342 Table A1: Specific capacitance measurements for Coplay Bridge

343 Table A2: Loss factor measurements for Coplay Bridge

344

Table A1: Specific capacitance measurements for Coplay Bridge						
Beam ID		AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Age of Grout [days]	Temperature [C]	[nF/m]	[nF/m]	[nF/m]	[nF/m]	[nF/m]
Prior to Tension	4.4	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Post-Tension	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
0	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
1	10.0	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
3	1.7	2.937	2.898	2.919	3.006	2.929
7	5.0	2.896	2.885	2.915	2.932	2.903
9	15.6	2.903	2.888	2.923	2.934	2.893
14	10.0	2.844	2.845	2.870	2.872	N.A.
16	7.2	2.845	2.867	2.896	2.879	2.833
17	3.3	2.829	2.851	2.864	2.858	2.813
28	5.6	2.830	2.845	2.858	2.862	2.817
42	3.3	2.824	2.838	2.861	2.856	2.816
86	-5.6	2.770	2.782	2.784	2.796	2.760
167	15.6	2.824	2.835	2.869	2.876	2.832
185	13.3	2.815	2.828	2.853	2.868	2.826
352	22.2	2.808	2.817	2.830	2.858	2.813

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347

Beam ID		AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Age of Grout [days]	Temperature [C]					
Prior to Tension	4.4	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
Post-Tension	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
0	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
1	10.0	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
3	1.7	0.671	0.595	1.093	0.690	0.931
7	5.0	0.597	0.531	0.981	0.565	0.848
9	15.6	0.557	0.493	0.963	0.502	0.761
14	10.0	0.395	0.364	0.666	0.371	N.A.
16	7.2	0.327	0.323	0.609	0.311	0.472
17	3.3	0.267	0.284	0.523	0.263	0.394
28	5.6	0.222	0.227	0.406	0.250	0.336
42	3.3	0.190	0.189	0.356	0.217	0.278
86	-5.6	0.088	0.098	0.154	0.126	0.119
167	15.6	0.125	0.145	0.253	0.198	0.213
185	13.3	0.106	0.123	0.219	0.163	0.172
352	22.2	0.052	0.060	0.093	0.089	0.086

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349

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